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Deliverable D5.6 – Mapping, action plan & strategic collaboration agreements with existing initiatives

TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITEIT EINDHOVEN

CESKE VYSOKE UCENI TECHNICKE V PRAZE

STAM

BRAINPORT DEVELOPMENT NV

SCIENCE CITY LYNGBY

DANMARKS TEKNISKE UNIVERSITET

IDEA STRATEGISCHE ECONOMISCHE CONSULTING

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COOrdinating and Piloting actions towards Era-hubs as inTer- and intra-regional Ecosystems for knowledge production

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Executive Summary

This document, titled “Mapping, action plan & strategic collaboration agreements with existing initiatives” presents a consolidated overview of COOPERATE’s efforts to map and demonstrate alignment with existing initiatives, instruments, networks, amongst others, which are relevant for the further development of ERA Hubs as inter- and intra-regional ecosystems for knowledge production. The Deliverable is structured around three main pillars: 1) mapping, 2) an action plan for further development of the COOPERATE Platform and 3) a draft collaboration agreement to facilitate inter-Hub cooperation.

The mapping exercise identifies and categorises over 100 relevant European projects, Alliances, programmes and networks, illustrating the rich landscape within which the COOPERATE landscape is embedded. This serves to highlight synergies and complementarities which can be further explored beyond the piloting phase for mutual learning, capacity building and strategic alignment.

The action plan outlines a development path to evolve the COOPERATE Platform (PLATFORM) beyond its current prototype state into a more mature, functional and user-friendly tool. Key recommendations are provided for technical improvements, user experience enhancements, organisational governance and monitoring and evaluation metrics.

Finally, the deliverable introduces a non-binding collaboration agreement template designed to support structured bilateral (or multilateral) partnerships between ERA Hubs.

List of abbreviation/Nomenclature

ACRONYM	STANDS FOR
CDE	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation
DX.X	Deliverable Number
ERA	European Research Area
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
SA	SELF-ASSESSMENT
TX.X	Task number
R&I	Research and Innovation
WP	Work Package

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1. Introduction

This Deliverable is produced under Task 5.3 of Work Package 5, which focuses on fostering coordination with existing European initiatives and instruments relevant to the development and institutionalisation of ERA Hubs. The approach adopted in this Deliverable is threefold. First, it presents a comprehensive mapping of projects, alliances, initiatives, and support mechanisms across the European R&I landscape. This mapping highlights potential areas of collaboration and mutual reinforcement. Second, the deliverable provides a structured action plan to guide the further development of the COOPERATE Platform (PLATFORM), which was launch in prototype state during this project. The Action Plan proposes technical, organisational and evaluative measures to improve usability and ensure long-term sustainability of the project results. Third, the deliverable presents a draft collaboration agreement (non-binding) which can be used by ERA Hubs to establish partnerships and underpin (future) joint actions across regional boundaries.

To build a coherent understanding of the European innovation landscape relevant to ERA Hubs, this Deliverable consolidates key EU-funded projects, university alliances, platforms and programmes, and strategic networks that can contribute to knowledge exchange, operational alignment, and systemic scaling of the COOPERATE approach.

2. Mapping

The COOPERATE project defines the ERA Hubs concept as an ecosystem of quadruple helix actors, led by universities, aiming at improving knowledge valorisation within their region. This mapping exercise identifies projects, alliances, programmes and organisations across the European R&I landscape that are conceptually aligned with the ERA Hubs model or offer resources, tools and partnerships that can reinforce its institutionalisation. The mapping has been structured into four key tables to facilitate understanding and strategic connection.

Table 1 lists selected EU-funded research and innovation projects. The entries include the project name, a brief description of its objectives, and areas of activity. Projects were selected based on their thematic focus and structural setup involving regional collaboration, ecosystem development, or capacity-building in research and innovation.

EU funded project and initiatives	
ERA_FABRIC	ERA_FABRIC is COOPERATE’s sister project and aims to create a structured “interconnected knowledge space” which directly parallels COOPERATE’s ambition to establish ERA Hubs as spaces for co-creation and stakeholder alignment.
INSPIRING ERA	The CSA INSPIRING ERA advances the ERA Policy Agenda and serves as a platform for knowledge sharing across ERA-related projects.
BOOST	BOOST builds cross-border innovation ecosystems across widening and non-widening regions, focussing on health, green and digital

	transitions. It mirrors COOPERATE’s objectives by piloting ecosystem collaboration and governance models among regional actors.
INNOVATE-EU	INNOVATE-EU supports deep-tech innovation through the integration of local ecosystems. Its efforts are placed on bridging the innovation divide and reinforcing capacity-building, both of which resonate with COOPERATE’s aim to engage less-connected innovation actors through ERA Hubs.
INTEGER	INTEGER’s “4 Helix Collaboratory” and focus on socially inclusive innovation offer a complementary conceptual model to COOPERATE’s co-creation arenas. Both focus on participatory governance and user-driven innovation.
3R-Connect	Although the 3R-Connect project is focused primarily on circular economy themes, the project also fosters regional ecosystem collaboration and joint strategy development.
Regions’ Alliances for Interconnected Startup Ecosystems	Directly aligned with COOPERATE’s goal of connecting regional innovation actors. It seeks to institutionalise regional collaboration, much like the long-term vision for ERA Hubs.

Table 1 EU funded project and initiatives

Table 2 presents alliances formed under the European Universities Initiative. It includes the name of each alliance, the number and type of member institutions, and a description of their joint activities. The focus is on institutional cooperation in areas such as education, research, mobility, digital transformation, and regional development.

University Alliances / European Universities initiative alliances	
EuroTech University Alliance	Strategic alliance of leading EU technical universities, focussed on collaborative research and innovation projects that address global challenges through technological advancement.
4EU+ Alliance	The 4EU+ Alliance is a group of eight research-intensive European universities collaborating to develop a shared, integrated approach to education, research and innovation. It focuses on four thematic areas: health, Europe in a changing world, digital transformation and environmental challenges, aiming to enable joint programmes, mobility and interdisciplinary collaboration across institutions.
ACE2EU Alliance	The Applied, Connected, Entrepreneurial and Engaged European University alliance brings together a group of diverse higher education institutions from across Europe. Its mission is to equip students, staff, researchers and external stakeholders with the knowledge, skills and competencies needed to collectively address future challenges, including digital transformation, green transitions

	and socio-economic issues. The alliance emphasises inclusivity, sustainability and transnational cooperation, aligning with core European values to drive societal transformation through education and innovation.
ARTEMIS Alliance	The ARTEMIS Alliance (Alliance for Regional Transition, Equality, Mobility, Inclusion and Sustainability) focuses on fostering collaboration in education, research and innovation to address regional and societal challenges. It aims to create a multilingual, inter-university campus that enhances mobility for students and staff, promotes inclusive education and supports sustainable regional development. It emphasises interdisciplinary approaches and partnerships with local communities to co-create solutions for issues such as sustainable mobility, digital transformation and social inclusion.
Across Alliance	The Across Alliance is a network of ten European universities working to enhance cooperation in education, research and innovation across Europe's cross-border regions. It supports joint programmes, international classrooms through seasonal schools and experimentation via seed funding. The alliance facilitates mobility and collaboration through shared digital tools, including a common course catalogue, an eCampus platform and a digital mobility guide, aiming to build an integrated and multicultural higher education area.
Arqus Alliance	The Arqus Alliance brings together nine research universities aiming to build a deep level of integration in education, research and innovation across Europe. It focusses on promoting multilingualism, inclusion, entrepreneurial education and civic engagement. Key areas of collaboration include joint educational programmes, open science initiatives, researcher mobility and fostering active European citizenship among students and staff.
Aurora Alliance	The Aurora Alliance is a consortium of research-intensive universities committed to using academic excellence to drive societal impact. It focuses on tackling global challenges through inclusive education, sustainability and innovation. The alliance promotes student and staff mobility, joint programmes and collaboration on areas such as climate change, digital society, health and social equity, aiming to align higher education with the UN Sustainable Development Goals.
BAUHAUS4EU Alliance	The BAUHAUS4EU Alliance brings together a consortium of ten European universities collaborating to establish a shared European campus which fosters innovation in education, research and regional development. Drawing inspiration from the New European Bauhaus initiative, the alliance emphasises sustainability, aesthetics and

	inclusivity in its approach to higher education.
CHALLENGE.EU Alliance	CHALLENGE.EU is a European University Alliance consisting of nine institutions aiming to advance interdisciplinary education, research and innovation. It focuses on three thematic areas: Health and Well-being, Smart Digitalisation, and Sustainable Futures, aligning with the UN Sustainable Development Goals. The alliance promotes collaboration among academia, industry, policymakers and society.
CHARM-EU Alliance	CHARM-EU (Challenge-driven, Accessible, Research-based, Mobile European University) is a European University Alliance focused on addressing global challenges through interdisciplinary and inclusive education. It promotes student mobility, sustainability and innovation and offers joint programmes. The alliance integrates research, education and societal impact in a transdisciplinary and challenge-based learning environment.
CIVICA Alliance	CIVICA is a European University Alliance consisting of ten leading institutions specialised in social sciences, humanities, business management and public policy. Its aim is to create a transnational interuniversity campus that integrates education, research and civic engagement. CIVICA focuses on fostering academic collaboration, promoting digital innovation and addressing societal challenges through interdisciplinary approaches.
CIVIS Alliance	CIVIS brings together ten universities which together work to create a transnational European campus focused on civic engagement, inclusivity and social responsibility. It promotes interdisciplinary engagement, inclusivity and social responsibility. It promotes interdisciplinary education and research across themes such as health, climate, digital transformation, democracy and cities. The alliance aims to strengthen the role of universities in society by fostering collaboration with local communities as well as international partners.
COLOURS Alliance	The COLOURS Alliance (COLlaborative innovative sUustainable Regional univerSities) is an alliance consisting of nine European universities. It aims to foster collaboration in education, research and innovation, emphasising sustainability and regional development. The alliance focuses on addressing societal challenges through interdisciplinary approaches and strengthening ties between universities and their local communities.
Circle U. Alliance	Circle U. Alliance brings together research-intensive universities aiming to promote excellence in education, research and innovation. It focuses on interdisciplinary collaboration around key societal challenges, particularly in the areas of climate, global health and

	<p>democracy. The alliance fosters student and staff mobility, joint programmes and partnerships with external stakeholders to enhance societal impact.</p>
E3UDRES2 Alliance	<p>E3UDRES2 (Engaged and Entrepreneurial European University as Driver for European Smart and Sustainable Regions) is an Alliance focused on strengthening small and medium-sized cities and their surrounding regions. It promotes smart and sustainable regional development through applied research, challenge-based learning and collaboration with local stakeholders. The alliance emphasises innovation, entrepreneurship and citizen engagement across disciplines and borders.</p>
EC2U Alliance	<p>The EC2U (European Campus of City-Universities) Alliance is a network of universities which are closely connected to their local cities, aiming to foster a shared space for education, research, innovation and social engagement. It promotes sustainable development, multilingualism and intercultural dialogue, with a strong emphasis on collaboration between universities and their urban communities. Key focus areas include health and well-being, sustainable cities and digital transformation.</p>
ECIU University	<p>ECIU University (European Consortium of Innovation Universities) is an Alliance focused on challenge-based learning, innovation and societal impact. It brings together learners, researchers and regional stakeholders to co-create solutions to real-world challenges, particularly aligned with the UN Sustainable Development Goals. The alliance offers flexible learning pathways, micro-credentials and strong links to regional ecosystems through transdisciplinary collaboration.</p>
EDUC Alliance	<p>The EDUC (European Digital UniverCity) Alliance is a network of universities working together to create a shared digital and physical space for education and research. It promotes students and staff mobility, joint programmes and virtual learning environments to support multilingual, interdisciplinary and inclusive education. The alliance focuses on digital transformation, active citizenship and addressing societal challenges through academic cooperation.</p>
EELISA Alliance	<p>EELISA (European Engineering Learning Innovation and Science Alliance) brings together European universities to redefine engineering education through a more inclusive, interdisciplinary and socially engaged approach. It aims to connect engineering with societal needs, promoting mobility, joint programmes and real-world challenge-based learning. EELISA fosters collaboration between students, academics and external stakeholders to develop solutions</p>

	aligned with sustainable development and civic responsibility.
EMERGE	The EMERGE Alliance (Empowering the Margins of Europe through Regional and Global Engagement) focuses on promoting inclusion, sustainability and multilingualism, particularly in Europe’s peripheral and less-represented regions. It places societal engagement at the core of its mission, combining flexible, challenge-based learning with regional knowledge and community collaboration. It supports lifelong learning through micro-credentials, encourages language diversity through plurilingual mobility schemes, and integrates academic pathways that are responsive to both local needs and global challenges.
ENGAGE.EU	ENGAGE.EU is an Alliance which unites universities with a strong expertise in social sciences, economics and management to tackle major societal challenges. It aims to equip students, researchers and citizens with the skills and knowledge needed to address issues such as digitalisation, climate change, ageing populations and social inequality. The alliance promotes interdisciplinary education, collaborative research and engagement with business, government and civil society, fostering an inclusive an impact-drive European learning community.
ENHANCE	The ENHANCE Alliance consists of technical universities working to create a joint framework for education, research and innovation grounded in societal needs. It focuses on promoting sustainable development, digital transformation and social equity by linking engineering and science with human-centred approaches. The alliance supports mobility, joint programmes and interdisciplinary collaboration, while actively engaging with external stakeholders to co-create solutions to complex global and regional challenges.
ENLIGHT	ENLIGHT brings together research-intensive universities to foster equitable, sustainable and global engagement in higher education. It focuses on addressing major societal challenges such as health, digitalisation, climate change and equity through transdisciplinary education, research collaboration and innovation. ENLIGHT promotes student and staff mobility, joint learning pathways and close cooperation with local communities and stakeholders, aiming to building inclusive knowledge ecosystems across Europe.
EPICUR	EPICUR (European Partnership for an Innovative Campus Unifying Regions) aims to build a connected and inclusive inter-university campus. It focuses on fostering multilingualism, liberal arts and sciences education and challenge-based learning across disciplines. EPICUR promotes mobility, interdisciplinary collaboration and civic

	engagement, aiming to prepare students and staff to navigate and contribute to a complex, diverse and rapidly changing Europe.
ERUA	ERUA (European Reform University Alliance) brings together universities committed to rethinking the role of higher education in society through openness, innovation and critical thinking. It emphasizes interdisciplinary teaching, research collaboration and active citizenship, particularly in relation to social transformation and sustainability. ERUA fosters inclusive learning environments, promotes mobility and encourages experimental academic practices that challenge traditional university models.
EU GREEN	The EU GREEN (European University Alliance for Sustainability, Responsible Growth, Inclusive Education and Environment) Alliance consists of universities which are committed to advancing sustainable development through education, research and innovation. It promotes interdisciplinary collaboration on environmental, social and economic challenges, aligning its activities with the UN Sustainable Development Goals. EU GREEN supports joint academic programmes, mobility and knowledge exchange aimed at building greener, more inclusive societies across Europe.
EU-CONEXUS	EU-CONEXUS (European University for Smart Urban Coastal Sustainability) is a transnational alliance focused on addressing sustainability challenges specific to urban and coastal regions. It promotes interdisciplinary education and research in areas such as blue growth, coastal resilience and sustainable urban development. It fosters mobility, joint degrees and strong cooperation with regional stakeholders, aiming to build a European university that responds to the needs of coastal communities through innovation and societal engagement.
EU-GIFT	EU-GIFT (European University for Geographical Identify as a Driver for Food Systems Transition to Sustainability) Alliance focuses on promoting excellence in education and research in areas such as viticulture, differentiated quality foods and sustainable agriculture. It aims to develop joint academic programmes, including degrees and micro-credentials, and to foster research and innovation that enhance the sustainability and resilience of regional food systems. By integrating education, research and community engagement, EU-GIFT seeks to contribute to the transformation of food systems in alignment with European values and sustainability goals.
EU4DUAL	The EU4DUAL (European Dual Studies University) Alliance is a consortium of higher education institutions dedicated to advancing dual education, combining academic learning with practical, on-the-

	<p>job training. By integrating theoretical instruction with real-world experience, the alliance aims to better prepare students for the evolving demands of the future workforce. EU4DUAL develops joint academic programs and fosters research collaborations aligned with its core themes.</p>
EUGLOH	<p>EUGLOH (European University Alliance for Global Health) brings together universities to collaborate on education, research and innovation in the field of global health. It takes a broad, interdisciplinary approach to health, addressing topics such as well-being, environmental sustainability, medical technologies and health economics. It promotes mobility, joint academic programmes and partnerships with industry and civil society to equip students and researchers with the skills needed to tackle global health challenges.</p>
EULiST	<p>The EULiST (European Universities Linking Society and Technology) Alliance brings together universities to bridge the gap between technological and social sciences. It aims to foster interdisciplinary education and research that address societal challenges through innovation, inclusion and sustainability. By promoting mobility, shared digital resources and collaborative learning environments, EULiST works to create a more integrated and socially responsive European higher education space.</p>
EUNICE	<p>EUNICE (European University for Customised Education) Alliance focuses on regional engagement and applied sciences to offer flexible, student-centred education across Europe. It aims to develop customised learning paths, foster intercultural and interdisciplinary skills and strengthen links between academia, industry and society. EUNICE supports mobility, joint programmes and challenge-based learning to prepare students for global citizenship and regional impact.</p>
EUNICoast	<p>The EUNICoast (European University of Islands, Ports and Coastal Territories) Alliance brings together universities situated in maritime regions, to form a transnational academic network focused on the sustainable development of coastal and island communities. It aims to enhance the collective capacity of associated universities to respond effectively to the societal and environmental challenges faced by island and coastal communities, such as climate change, biodiversity loss, economic diversification and social inclusion.</p>
EUPeace	<p>EUPeace (European University for Peace, Justice and Inclusive Societies) Alliance is committed to cultivating the conditions necessary for peace, justice and inclusion through education, research and societal engagement. Its research is organised into</p>

	<p>thematic hubs focusing on areas such as security and conflict transformation, climate science and just transition, migration and human rights, and inclusive health and well-being. The hubs promote cross-disciplinary collaboration and aim to translate academic knowledge into practical solutions.</p>
EURECA-PRO	<p>EURECA-PRO (European University on Responsible Consumption and Production) Alliance brings together universities committed to advancing education and research aligned with the UN Sustainable Development Goal 12 (<i>Responsible consumption and production</i>). It focuses on the topic by fostering interdisciplinary collaboration, sustainability-driven innovation and critical thinking. EURECA-PRO supports joint programmes, mobility opportunities and partnerships with industry and society to promote systemic change towards sustainable lifestyles and economies.</p>
EUTOPIA Alliance	<p>The EUTOPIA Alliance works to create a connected and inclusive academic community. It focuses on challenge-based learning, open science and collaborative research that addresses pressing global and societal issues. It promotes student and staff mobility, joint programmes and cross-institutional teaching and research, aiming to prepare graduates for a diverse, interconnected and rapidly changing world.</p>
EUniWell	<p>EUniWell (European University for Well-Being) Alliance is committed to promoting individual, societal and environmental well-being through education, research and engagement. It focuses on themes such as health, equality, sustainability and quality of life, aligning its' activities with the UN Sustainable Development Goals. The alliance fosters interdisciplinary collaboration, student and staff mobility and partnerships with stakeholders to develop inclusive, evidence-based approaches to well-being across Europe.</p>
EUonAIR	<p>The EUonAIR (European University on AI in Curricula, Smart UniverCity and Mobility) brings together business and technical universities. It aims to transform higher education by responsibly integrating AI into teaching, research and mobility. EUonAIR focusses on developing innovative, inclusive and ethical AI-driven educational models that address societal challenges and support sustainable development.</p>
EUt+	<p>EUt+ (European University of Technology) Alliance consists of technical universities, united by the vision of creating a human-centred, inclusive and sustainable model of higher education. It aims to redefine the role of technology in society by integrating engineering, sciences, humanities and social sciences inter</p>

	interdisciplinary curricula. EUt+ emphasizes inclusivity, multilingualism and the development of responsible technologists equipped to address global challenges.
EuroTeQ Alliance	The EuroTeQ Alliance consists of leading technical and business universities aiming to transform engineering education through interdisciplinary collaboration, innovation and societal engagement. It focuses on developing flexible learning pathways, fostering challenge-based learning environments and promoting lifelong learning to equip students and professionals with the skills needed to address global challenges.
FORTHEM	FORTHEM (Fostering Outreach within European Regions through Transnational Higher Education Mobility) promotes inclusive, collaborative and interdisciplinary education and research. It focuses on strengthening regional engagement, expanding mobility opportunities, and supporting civic involvement through challenge-based learning and joint initiatives. IT emphasizes co-creation with societal stakeholders and fosters multilingualism, cultural exchange and innovation across its transnational campus.
HEROES	The HEROES (Higher Education for Resilience-Oriented and Empowered Societies) Alliance focuses on enhance smart regional resilience through digital innovation, practice-oriented education and applied research. Its mission is to empower students, professionals and communities to anticipate, adapt to and recover from disruptions by strategically leveraging technologies such as AI, Extended Reality and telehealth.
INGENIUM	INGENIUM aims to create a fully integrated inter-university campus that enhances education, research and societal engagement across Europe. Central to its mission is the development of joint degree programmes, mobility for students and staff and collaborative research initiatives. It emphasizes inclusivity, sustainability and digital innovation, aligning its activities with the UN Sustainable Development Goals and the EU Green Deal.
INVEST	The INVEST (Innovations of Regional Sustainability) Alliance focuses on fostering sustainable regional development through interdisciplinary education, research and innovation. Its core mission is to equip students and staff with the skills and knowledge necessary to lead to sustainable transformations in their communities. Its primary focus areas are the Water-Energy-Food-Environment Nexus, Quality of Life and Entrepreneurship.
NEOLAiA	NEOLAiA is committed to fostering inclusion, democracy and innovation in higher education. It aims to enhance regional

	<p>connectivity, prevent populism through academic mobility and strengthen inclusion and interculturalism by establishing common standards to eliminate barriers for underrepresented groups. NEOLAiA focuses on increasing regional research impact by leveraging existing regional specialisation strengths and promoting knowledge transfer through open science.</p>
NeurotechEU	<p>NeurotechEU is dedicated to advancing neurotechnology through interdisciplinary education, research and innovation. It aims to build a trans-European network of excellence in brain research and technologies, enhancing the competitiveness of European education, research, economy and society. NeurotechEU focuses on eight dimensions, including empirical and clinical neuroscience, neuromorphic computing, neuroprosthetics and neurometaphysics, to foster innovation and address societal challenges.</p>
OpenEU Alliance	<p>The OpenEU Alliance aims to establish the first pan-European open university, focusing on digital transformation, inclusivity and lifelong learning. By leveraging the collective expertise of leading open and distance learning institutions, OpenEU seeks to provide accessible, high-quality education to diverse learners, including non-traditional students and underrepresented groups. Through its initiatives, OpenEU aims to strengthen the digital, green and social dimensions of the European Higher Education Area, ensuring that quality education is accessible to all.</p>
PIONEER	<p>The PIONEER Alliance is committed to advancing UN Sustainable Development Goal 11: ‘Sustainable Cities and Communities’. Focused on urban sustainability, PIONEER aims to develop inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable cities by fostering interdisciplinary education, research and innovation. PIONEER emphasizes collaboration with regional ecosystems, engaging stakeholders such as local authorities, businesses and citizens to co-create solutions addressing urban challenges.</p>
RUN-EU	<p>RUN-EU (Regional University Network – European University) Alliance aims to strengthen regional development by providing students, researchers and academics with green, digital and inclusive skills, thereby enhancing the competitiveness of their regions and reducing existing regional development disparities in Europe. It focuses on creating a European Zone for Interregional Development through the establishment of European Innovation Hubs in three thematic areas: Future and Sustainable Industries, Bioeconomy and Social Innovation. These hubs serve as collaborative platforms for education, research and innovation, engaging with regional stakeholders to address</p>

	societal challenges.
SEA-EU	The SEA-EU Alliance brings together coastal universities with the aim to create a unified “European Coastal Campus” that fosters transnational cooperation in education, research and innovation, with a particular focus on marine and maritime disciplines. Its mission emphasizes sustainable development, inclusivity and regional engagement and it supports open science, lifelong learning and the co-creation of knowledge with societal partners to address global challenges and contribute to the UN Sustainable Development Goals.
STARS EU	STARS EU Alliance consists of universities from non-capital regions, established to drive regional transformation through collaborative education, research and innovation. It focuses on developing innovative, flexible and challenge-based educational and research systems that address societal challenges and promote sustainable development. STARS EU emphasizes regional engagement, aiming to create a European university model that accelerates regional development by establishing strong alliances with key industries and sectors.
SUNRISE	SUNRISE (Smaller (Strategic) Universities Network for Regional Innovative and Sustainable Evolution) brings together a group of smaller-sized European universities located in non-metropolitan regions and aims to enhance the strategic role of these institutions in fostering sustainable regional development through education, research, innovation and societal engagement. With a strong focus on STEAM disciplines, it promotes interdisciplinary collaboration and the development of innovative, flexible study programmes.
Transform4Europe (T4EU)	T4EU is committed to fostering transformation through education, research and regional engagement. It aims to build an integrated, multilingual and inclusive European University that educates ‘knowledge entrepreneurs’ – individuals equipped with interdisciplinary, entrepreneurial, digital and intercultural competencies to drive societal change. T4EU focuses on three core areas: digital transformation and smart regions; environmental transformation and sustainability; and societal transformation, community building and inclusion.
ULYSSEUS	ULYSSEUS Alliance is committed to creating an open, person-centred and entrepreneurial European University by 2030. Its mission is to foster excellence in education, research and innovation, while promoting European values and global engagement. Central to ULYSSEUS is its Innovation Ecosystem, comprising Innovation Hubs that address key societal challenges such as ageing and wellbeing,

	sustainable energy, digitalisation, AI, tourism and circular economy. These hubs facilitate interdisciplinary collaboration, knowledge transfer and citizen involvement.
UNIC	The UNIC Alliance brings together European universities situated in post-industrial cities, committed to transforming higher education through collaboration, innovation and inclusion. UNIC focuses on addressing the challenges and opportunities of urban transformation by integrating education, research and societal engagement. It fosters “Engaged Research”, encouraging collaboration between academia, citizens and city stakeholders to co-create solutions for urban challenges.
UNINOVIS	UNINOVIS Alliance – Data for L.I.F.E. – aims to establish a transnational European university focused on applied data science with full operational capacity by 2027. Its mission is encapsulated in acronym L.I.F.E.: Lifelong learning in data; Integrating innovation ecosystems; Fostering green and digital transitions; European excellence in data competencies.
UNITA	The UNITA Alliance (Universitas Montium) brings together universities which are primarily located in rural, mountainous and cross-border regions. It aims to create an inclusive, multilingual and research-driven European inter-university campus that fosters regional development and European integration. Its mission encompasses several key objectives: developing flexible, student-centred education; promoting multilingualism through the comprehension of Romance languages; enhancing mobility opportunities, including rural and virtual exchanges; and strengthening research and innovation in areas such as renewable energies, cultural heritage and circular economy.
UNIVERSEH	The UNIVERSEH Alliance (European Space University for Earth and Humanity) aims to develop a new model of collaboration in the field of space, fostering interdisciplinary education, research and innovation across Europe. The alliance envisions creating an inclusive, multilingual and sustainable inter-university campus that addresses the challenges and opportunities of the evolving space sector.
UNIGreen	UNIGreen Alliance brings together institutions dedicated to advancing sustainability through education, research and innovation and aims to equip students and professionals with the skills needed for a climate-neutral and resource-efficient economy. UNIGreen emphasizes inclusivity, multilingualism and the integration of European values, fostering a diverse and engaged academic community.

U!REKA SHIFT	U!REKA SHIFT (Urban Research and Education Knowledge Alliance) focuses on fostering sustainable urban development through education, research and innovation. It aims to accelerate the transition towards climate-neutral and smart cities by 2030, aligning with the EU’s mission on 100 Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities. It builds on three Centres of Expertise focussing on: Transition to Circular Societies, Climate-Neutral Urban Communities, and Innovative Governance & Citizen Engagement.
Una Europa	Una Europa brings together leading European research universities with the mission to create a truly European inter-university environment that fosters collaboration in education, research and innovation across borders. It aims to develop joint educational offerings sustainable for future graduates, ensuring they are equipped to thrive in an interconnected and rapidly changing world. Una Europa focuses on six interdisciplinary research areas; Cultural Heritage, Data Science & AI, European Studies, One Health and Sustainability.
Unite!	Unite! (University Network for Innovation, Technology and Engineering) Alliance is focused on innovation, technology and engineering and aims to create a trans-European campus that fosters collaboration in education, research and innovation. Its mission is to educate future European and global experts equipped with skills essential for the digital and green transitions.
YUFE	The YUFE (Young Universities for the Future of Europe) Alliance aims to build a student-centred, open and inclusive European University that transcends national borders and fosters collaboration among academia, industry, government and civil society. Its mission is to transform European higher education by offering flexible, personalised learning pathways that combine academic excellence with civic engagement and professional development. Through its Virtual Campus students can access a diverse range of courses, language programmes and mobility opportunities across partner institutions.

Table 2 University Alliances / European Universities initiative alliances

Table 3 outlines relevant EU platforms, programmes, and instruments that provide structural support for regional innovation. ERA Hubs can draw from these to enhance digital, financial and policy frameworks within their ecosystems.

EU Platforms, Programmes & Instruments	
European Innovation Ecosystems (EIE) programme	The EIE programme aims to create more connected and inclusive innovation ecosystems across Europe by strengthening collaboration among regional actors and facilitating the scaling of innovative solutions. This aligns with COOPERATE's goal to connect innovation ecosystems and provide ecosystem actors with tools to develop their ecosystem and collaborate across borders.
European Digital Innovation Hubs (EDIHs)	EDHIS support SMEs and public organisations with digital transformation through access to testing infrastructure, innovation services, and finance advice. ERA Hubs can integrate EDIHs as ecosystem support actors to help regional stakeholders access digital expertise and resources beyond their borders.
Regional Innovation Valleys	RIVs aim to strengthen innovation capacity across European regions by connecting regions with shared thematic priorities. COOPERATE and ERA Hubs can contribute to this agenda by identifying complementary ecosystems and facilitating cross-regional collaboration in strategic sectors, thereby helping to bridge the innovation divide.
Interregional Innovation Investments Instrument (I3)	The I3 instrument funds interregional partnerships aiming to scale up and commercialise joint innovation projects in shared S3 priority areas. The COOPERATE platform can support early-stage development of such partnerships by identifying synergies between ecosystems and preparing them for future I3 funding opportunities.
Smart Specialisation (S3) Platform	The S3 Platform supports regions in developing and implementing Smart Specialisation Strategies and facilitates interregional cooperation. S3 priorities can be used by COOPERATE and ERA Hubs for ecosystem profiling and matchmaking, ensuring that regional collaboration is rooted in shared strategic priorities.
Open Innovation Test Beds (OITs)	OITBs offer access to physical and digital testing environments for the development and validation of new materials and products. Integration of these facilities in ERA Hub (profiles) can help regional companies access shared infrastructure and innovation support.
URBACT	URBACT is a European Territorial Cooperation programme that facilitates transnational learning and exchange among cities. Its structured methodology for co-creation and policy learning is directly applicable to COOPERATE's ecosystem development and stakeholder engagement activities, especially in urban-focused regions.

Table 3 EU Platforms, Programmes & Instruments

Table 4 compiles a selection of European-level networks and umbrella organisations. It includes each organisation’s name, target membership (e.g., universities, SMEs, public bodies), and a summary of its main activities. Areas covered include policy dialogue, innovation support, regional development, and stakeholder coordination.

Key networks and organisations	
ERRIN – European Regions Research and Innovation Network	The ERRIN network with over 125 regional stakeholders focused on research and innovation policy, project development and knowledge exchange has long-standing experience with place-based innovation policy. The connection with COOPERATE can yield access to regional innovation actors, policy discussion and collaborative opportunities to better position ecosystems within broader EU dialogues and networks.
EEN – Enterprise Europe Network	EEN is a vast network that supports SMEs in innovating and growing internationally through tailored support, partnerships and advice. ERA Hubs can benefit from EEN’s services by connecting local SMEs to international partners, while EEN nodes may act as enablers within the COOPERATE framework.
ECIU – European Consortium of Innovative Universities	ECIU is a network of forward-looking European universities committed to challenge-based learning, innovation and societal impact through transdisciplinary collaboration. The consortium actively promotes regional engagement, lifelong learning and co-creation between academia, industry and public authorities. This mission is well aligned with COOPERATE’s aim to strengthen regional innovation ecosystems by centrally positioning universities as key actors and enablers within innovation ecosystems.
Eureka Network	The Eureka Network supports cross-border, market-driven industrial R&D and innovation projects among SMEs, corporates, research centres and universities and fosters international collaboration and access to funding for innovative companies. The complementarity between Eureka and COOPERATE lies in support to move ecosystem actors from early matchmaking and capacity-building into funded collaborative projects.
EIT – European Institute of Innovation and Technology	EIT Knowledge and Innovation Communities bring together business, academia and cities to drive innovation in specific domains. Integrating relevant EIT communities into ERA Hubs stakeholder engagement processes allows for relevant connections between regional actors with European knowledge hubs and co-investment opportunities.
ICLEI Europe – Local Governments for	ICLEI is a network of cities and regions committed to sustainable urban development through innovation, participation and resilience.

Sustainability	ICLEI’s focus on urban-regional sustainability directly supports ERA Hubs focussed on green transition and societal challenges, especially in smart and climate-oriented domains.
ECCP – European Cluster Collaboration Platform	ECCP connects cluster organisations across Europe, facilitating interregional cooperation, joint projects and EU engagement. ECCP is highly complementary to COOPERATE’s objective of strengthening cluster-led ecosystem development and offers a structured channel to promote COOPERATE tools, such as the prototype platform, to a pan-European audience of innovation clusters.
TAFTIE – The European Network of Innovation Agencies	TAFTIE is a high-level forum of national innovation agencies that shapes innovation policy, instruments and evaluation across Europe. While national in scope, TAFTIE’s best practices and strategic orientations can inform COOPERATE’s policy alignment and offer models for ecosystem support instruments at regional levels.
EURADA – European Association of Development Agencies	EURADA represent development agencies across Europe, supporting them in fostering economic growth and innovation in their regions. COOPERATE can engage with these agencies that act as ecosystem orchestrators, enabling the dissemination of tools, sharing of good practices and the expansion of the COOPERATE methodology to a wider regional base.

Table 4 Key networks and organisations

3. Action Plan

The COOPERATE project delivered a prototype PLATFORM which is made accessible through the COOPERATE website. The objective of the PLATFORM is three-fold; firstly, it serves to inspire emerging and aspiring ERA Hubs by showcasing existing ones, secondly it enables benchmarking (comparing results of the SELF-ASSESSMENT of different ERA Hubs) and finally it facilitates connectivity and promotes interaction between regional ecosystems. In order to further develop the PLATFORM beyond the prototype stage, it is important to have a structured overview and approach for future developments.

The next phase of the PLATFORM should aim to:

- Support recognition, visibility and networking among ERA Hubs and regional innovation ecosystems;
- Provide interactive, up-to-date and comparative information on ERA Hubs, and;
- Enable matchmaking, peer learning and collaboration.

In order to realise these aims it will be necessary to address both the technical and organisational side as well as future monitoring and evaluation.

Technical Developments

The following steps can be undertaken to elevate the PLATFORM to the next level;

- Solidifying the technical foundation:
 - o The platform would benefit from migrating from Microsoft PowerBI (the current back-end programme) to an EC-standard, thus ensuring compatibility with EU/EC systems and harmonise the 'look and feel' of EU/EC platforms;
 - o Ensure full GDPR compliance;
 - o Potentially build a basic backend interface to allow for decentralised content updating by authorised regional stakeholders.
- Improving the User Interface & Experience:
 - o Redesign the User Interface for better recognisability with ERA and EU/EC branding;
 - o Addition of tool-tips and micro-interactions to improve user friendliness of the Platform;
 - o Integrate responsive design to enable access across different devices such as desktop/laptop, tablets and mobiles;
- Feature expansion & interactivity:
 - o Addition of a search and filter functionality in order to be able to search by region, domain, maturity score, etc.;
 - o Introduction of click-through links to ERA Hub websites and e.g. the SELF-ASSESSMENT, PLAYBOOK, TOOLBOX, etc.;
 - o Enable secure contact forms or messaging gateways to allow for direct communication;
 - o Allow for direct ERA Hub comparison via e.g. maturity radar chart overlays;
 - o Establish API endpoints to allow for integration with other platforms.

Organisational developments

Beyond the technical developments, additional organisational developments will need to take place to ensure that the PLATFORM (and ERA Hub network) is effectively managed. Points to consider are:

- Platform governance: allocating clear ownership and right of management;
- Stakeholder involvement: engage ERA Hubs (present and future) to co-design features and test releases, and;
- Altered/improved access model: keeping public information and content available whilst integrating login for gated features such as contact forms.

Monitoring and evaluation

In order to effectively track the development and performance of the Platform, it will be essential to establish KPIs such as;

- Number of ERA Hubs listed / updated per quarter;
- Number of monthly Platform visits or users / session duration;
- Number of user-initiated contacts or interactions, and;
- Quality of user-feedback.

4. Collaboration Agreements

One of the key ambitions of the COOPERATE project has been to strengthen connectivity and alignment between regional innovation ecosystems through the development of the ERA Hub Framework model. As part of this ambition, fostering structured and sustainable interregional cooperation is essential. To support this, COOPERATE encourages the use of bilateral (or multilateral) collaboration agreements between ERA Hubs. These agreements serve as practical instruments to formalise cooperation (in a non-legally binding way), clarify the scope of the collaboration and the general principles. It provides a mechanism for exchanging expertise, coordinating strategic actions and increasing the visibility and impact of participating Hubs. The following section presents a draft template of a Collaboration Agreement which can be adapted and utilised by ERA Hubs to fit their collaboration purpose;

[DRAFT] COLLABORATION AGREEMENT

BETWEEN

[ERA Hub A], represented by [XXX], and;

[ERA Hub B], represented by [XXX]

PURPOSE

The purpose of this Agreement is to facilitate collaboration between the Parties – two ERA Hubs – within the framework of the European Research Area (ERA). The collaboration aims to strengthen regional research and innovation ecosystems, foster mutual learning and contribute to shared objectives in line with the ERA Policy Agenda. Through this partnership, the ERA Hubs intend to:

- Share knowledge and best practices to reinforce the capacities of research and innovation ecosystems;
- Explore opportunities from mutual learning that support innovation-driven regional and European economic growth;
- Promote joint visibility, communication and dissemination activities to enhance stakeholder engagement and policy impact;
- Align efforts with relevant EU strategies and funding instruments, including Horizon Europe and the European Innovation Ecosystems (EIE) programme.

SCOPE OF COLLABORATION

This collaboration may include, but is not limited to:

- Co-organising events, workshops, or policy dialogues on innovation and ecosystem development;
- Sharing ecosystem intelligence, methodologies, or stakeholder insights (non-confidential);
- Developing joint contributions to European for a, platforms or policy feedback processes;
- Promoting each other's initiatives, success cases and opportunities for cross regional collaboration.

GENERAL PRINCIPLES

The parties agree to:

- Engage in good faith and on the basis of trust and reciprocity;

- Respect the confidentiality of any shared information, where applicable;
- Preserve their institutional autonomy and freedom to pursue individual strategies.

DURATION AND TERMINATION

This Agreement is non-binding and shall remain in effect unless and until either Party provides written notice of its intention to terminate the collaboration.

MISCELLANEOUS

- This Agreement does not create financial obligations or legal commitments of any kind.
- Future collaboration involving funding, joint application, or formal partnerships may be subject to separate written arrangements.

SIGNATURES

For [ERA Hub A]:

For [ERA Hub B]:

5. Conclusion

As the COOPERATE project reaches its conclusion, Deliverable D5.6 marks one of the final outputs, consolidating key findings and tools developed to support the institutionalisation of ERA Hubs. This deliverable provides a comprehensive mapping of relevant European initiatives, a forward-looking action plan for the PLATFORM, and a practical template for collaboration agreements.

The action plan outlines recommendations to evolve the PLATFORM beyond its prototype state, with a focus on technical upgrades, user experience enhancements, governance models, and monitoring indicators. These guidelines are intended to support future custodians of the platform in maintaining its relevance and impact.

The collaboration agreement template included herein offers ERA Hubs a structured, flexible framework to initiate and formalise bilateral or multilateral cooperation. While non-binding, it provides clarity of intent and can serve as a first step toward deeper and more strategic partnerships.